

Unravelling charge dynamic effects in photocatalytic CO₂ reduction over TiO₂: Anatase vs P25

Laura Collado, Miguel García-Tecedor, Miguel Gomez-Mendoza, Alejandro Herrero Pizarro, Freddy E. Oropeza, Marta Liras, Víctor A. de la Peña O'Shea **

Photoactivated Processes Unit, IMDEA Energy Institute, Parque Tecnológico de Móstoles, Avda. Ramón de la Sagra 3, 28935 Móstoles, Madrid, Spain.

Abstract

Among different TiO₂ polymorphs, anatase has been way more studied than rutile in photocatalytic CO₂ reduction. In the present work, the catalytic activity of anatase and P25-TiO₂ (mixture between anatase and rutile phases) has been evaluated in gas-phase CO₂ photoreduction. The interfacial heterojunction between anatase and rutile in P25 leads to a superior photocatalytic activity. Differences in the catalytic performance of sole TiO₂ anatase and P25 are investigated by a set of optoelectronic and electrochemical characterization techniques. Our results show that the higher CO₂ reduction activity of P25 is due to an enhanced charge separation at the anatase/rutile interface, and thermodynamically more favorable band energy positions towards CO₂ reaction products.

1. Introduction

One of the most important challenges of our Society is the development of sustainable technologies for the reduction of pollutants and greenhouse effects. The transcendence of these actions was reflected in the Paris Agreement on Climate Change [1], which accorded to limit the global temperature increase to 2 °C by 2100, with respect to the pre-industrial levels. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) estimated that this objective will be only accomplished if there is a drastic reduction of the CO₂ emissions between 40-70% by 2050 [2]. This has been recently reaffirmed in the 2021 United Nations Climate Change Conference, recognizing that a 45% CO₂ emission reduction is needed to limit the rise of temperature to 1.5°C by 2030 [3].

Nowadays, 80% of the global energy demand for transportation and chemical industry is still covered by fossil fuels (coal, oil, gas) [4]. Aiming to fight against Climate Change, a new generation of efficient technologies and materials have been developed along the last years to tackle harmful emissions. Particular attention has attracted the development of sustainable routes for CO₂ conversion into fuels, simultaneously contributing to mitigate the effects of global warming while providing a solution to the growing energy demand [5,6]. In this context, artificial photosynthesis (AP) technologies convert abundant raw materials (CO₂, H₂O, N₂ or biomass) into solar fuels and building-block chemicals (C₁-C₂, H₂ and NH₃) powered by solar energy instead of conventional fossil fuels [7,8]. Despite the potential of this technology and the great scientific and technological achievements to date, conversion efficiencies are still very low for practical application [9].

Photocatalytic CO₂ reduction is a particular AP technology that involves the simultaneous water oxidation and CO₂ reduction, following proton-coupled electron

transfer (PCET) processes. The high complexity of this reaction generally leads to non-selective multi-electron pathways that yield a great variety of by-products, mainly hydrocarbons and oxygenated compounds [10–16]. Besides, this process is very sensitive to several factors involving the nature of the catalyst (i.e. surface area, acid-basic character of the catalyst surface, carbonaceous deposits, oxygen deficient surfaces, etc.) as well as the operational conditions (i.e. irradiance, pH, sacrificial agents, presence of O₂ traces, purity of reagents, etc.) [9,17,18]. Consequently, the lack of standardization of experimental conditions and evaluation criteria result in a high dispersion of production yields [19] and hardly comparable data, which is clearly limiting the development of this technology [9].

Among catalysts, TiO₂ is the most studied semiconductor for CO₂ photoreduction and considered as benchmark material for these studies due to its strong redox ability, availability, non-toxicity and low cost compared to other materials [19,20]. TiO₂ exists in one of its three polymorphs: anatase, rutile and brookite, with bandgap (E_g) energies ranging from 3.0 - 3.2 eV (i.e. 413 - 387 nm), which limit their photoactivity to the UV wavelength range. Despite rutile is the most stable phase among its three polymorphs and has a smaller bandgap than anatase (ca. 3.03 and 3.20 eV, respectively), most photocatalytic studies are focused on TiO₂ anatase rather than rutile [21,22]. In general, the anatase phase has a higher conduction band energy, Fermi level, and lower electron–hole recombination rate than rutile, which are, all important characteristics that make it more applicable in photo(electro)catalytic applications.

The majority of the authors focused on the use of A-TiO₂, while the catalytic performance of R-TiO₂ or the mixture between both phases has been less studied [23,24]. P25 (Degussa) is a mixture of anatase and rutile, typical composition 70-

80% anatase and 10-20% rutile [25], which generally shows a synergistic effect between the two phases in the heterojunction for photocatalytic applications [26,27]. Recently, the synergistic effect between anatase and rutile has been evaluated for the CO₂ photoreduction [28–30], showing that P25 can display a higher catalytic activity than the anatase and rutile phases separately [31,32]. Some works reported that the interface structure between rutile and anatase plays an important role in the migration of electrons and holes, improving the photocatalytic hydrogen and oxygen evolution compared to the individual phases [33]. However, there is no consensus regarding the band alignments between rutile and anatase phases [34–36] and the consequent charge separation pathway [33,36–40], being still a hot topic of debate among the scientific community.

Aiming to contribute in this scientific debate, this study pretends to unravel the impact of charge dynamic and its effect on the synergistic interaction between anatase and rutile phases (present in P25), for an enhanced photocatalytic CO₂ performance.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Commercial anatase TiO₂ nanoparticles were acquired from Crystal ACTIV™ (PC500, Lot No. 6293000586), while commercial anatase/rutile heterojunction, TiO₂ Aeroxide® P25, was purchased from Evonik-Degussa GmbH. Prior to use, both samples were calcined at 400 °C for 4 h at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹.

2.2. General characterization

Crystal structures of TiO₂- Anatase and P25 were characterized with an X-ray diffractometer (Philips PW 3040/00 X'Pert MPD/MRD) with Cu K α radiation ($k =$

1.54178 Å) at a scanning rate of 0.2° s⁻¹. The anatase/rutile fraction was calculated according to Eq. (1) [41]:

$$[A]/\% = \frac{100 \times I_A}{I_A + 1.265 \times I_R} \quad (1)$$

Where I_A and I_R correspond to the areas of anatase (1 0 1) and rutile (1 1 0) XRD peaks, respectively.

Specific surface areas were calculated from N₂ adsorption–desorption isotherms at 77 K using a QUADRA-SORB instrument. The samples were previously outgassed at 105°C during 20 h under N₂. Pore size distribution of meso-pores was analyzed by BJH method. The size and morphology of the particles were observed with a Philips Technai 20 Transmission Electron Microscope, operating with a tungsten filament working at 200 kV with a resolution of 0.27 nm equipped with a with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDS) used for the semiquantitative chemical elemental analysis. UV–VIS diffuse reflectance spectra (UV–Vis DRS) of solid powdered samples were obtained with a Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050 UV/Vis/NIR spectrometer. Quantification of the band gap transition was calculated from the steep shape of the spectra and the equation $\alpha h\nu = A(h\nu - E_g)^m$ was used where the absorption coefficient (α) is related to the incident photon energy ($h\nu$), A is constant, m is the index indicating the type of transition.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) of samples was done in a lab-based spectrometer (SPECS GmbH, Berlin) using a monochromated Al K α 1 source ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) at 50 W, and a 300 μ m a spot size. The samples were studied on a 180° hemi-spherical energy analyzer (SPECS PHOIBOS 150 NAP analyzer) with 150 mm mean radius, equipped with a nozzle with a 300 μ m diameter orifice. The

total energy resolution of the measurements was about 0.5 eV. The binding energy (BE) was calibrated against the Fermi level (E_F) of Au.

2.3. Photoelectrochemical characterization

Photoelectrodes preparation. For the preparation of the electrodes, a viscous paste was fabricated with the precursor powders following a previously reported method [42]. Precursor powders of P25 and anatase were suspended in isopropanol and turned into viscous pastes upon its addition on a solution of 10 wt. % of ethyl cellulose (30–70 mPa·s from Sigma-Aldrich) in α -terpineol. The isopropanol was evaporated through a Rotavapor. The pastes were deposited by doctor blade on the ITO substrates and then calcinated at 450 °C during 30 min in order to remove all organic compounds.

Photoelectrochemical measurements. Experiments were performed under three-electrode configuration in an electrochemical cell with a quartz window containing an aqueous solution of 0.5 M Na_2SO_3 . An Ag/AgCl electrode was employed as the reference, a Pt wire as the counter electrode and the fabricated photoelectrode as the working electrode. These experiments were performed with a potentiostat-galvanostat PGSTAT204 provided with an integrated impedance module FRA11 (10 mV of modulation amplitude). A solar simulator (LOT LSH302 Xe lamp and an LSZ389 AM1.5 global filter) calibrated as 1 Sun (100 mW/cm²) was used as a light source. The applied potentials were referred to the Reversible Hydrogen Electrode (RHE) using the Nernst equation: $V_{RHE} = V_{Ag/AgCl} + V^0_{Ag/AgCl} + 0.059 \cdot pH$. The exposed area of the sample to the electrolyte was 1 cm².

2.4. Photophysical characterization

Steady-state and Time-Resolved Photoluminescence. Photoluminescence (PL) experiments for powdered samples were carried out with a Fluorescence Spectrometer Perkin Elmer LS 55, with an excitation wavelength of 300 nm and using a cut-off filter at 350 nm in front-face mode. Time resolved Photoluminescence (TRPL) for powdered samples was measured using the Time-Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC) technique, and recorded in a Mini Tau system from Edinburgh Instruments, using an EPL-375 picosecond pulsed diode laser with emission at 372 nm as excitation source (with a band-pass filter of 450 nm). The decays were adjusted by a tri-exponential fit. The average photoluminescence (τ_F) was obtained following the equation: $\langle \tau \rangle = \frac{\sum (A_i * \tau_i^2)}{\sum (A_i * \tau_i)}$, in which A_i is the amplitude of each lifetime τ_i .

Transient Absorption Spectroscopy. Nanosecond Transient absorption spectroscopy (TAS) measurements were carried out with a LP980 equipment from Edinburgh Instruments based on an optical parametric oscillator (OPO) pumped by the third harmonic of a Nd:YAG laser (EKSPLA). The excitation wavelength for the measurements was 355 nm with single energy pulses of 1.5 mJ/pulse of ca. 5 ns duration while a pulsed Xenon flash lamp (150 W) was employed as detecting light source. The probe light is dispersed through a monochromator (TMS302-A, grating 150 lines/mm) after it has passed the sample and then reaches a PMT detector (Hamamatsu Photonics) to obtain the temporal profile. The absorbance of all samples was kept at ~ 0.25 at $\lambda_{exc} = 355$ nm as dispersed solutions in Milli-Q water. All transient spectra were recorded at room temperature using 10 x 10 mm² quartz cells, which were bubbled for 15 min with N₂ before acquisition.

2.5. CO₂ photoreduction. Gas-phase CO₂ photoreduction experiments were performed in continuous-flow mode using a stain-steel photoreactor (280 mL) provided with a borosilicate window for illumination. Solid catalysts (0.1 g) were supported over a glass microfiber filter and fitted inside the reactor. A mixture of CO₂ (99.9999%, Praxair) and water vapor (CO₂:H₂O = 7.25 molar ratio) was produced in a Controller Evaporator Mixer (CEM) and fed continuously to the reactor. Photocatalytic experiments were carried out at 2 bar and 50 °C. The catalysts were illuminated using four 6W lamps Philips Actinic ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 369 \text{ nm}$) with an average intensity of 47.2 W m^{-2} (measured by a Blue-Wave spectrometer in the range 330–400 nm) (**Fig. S1**). Reaction products were analyzed in continuous mode using a gas chromatograph (Agilent 7890 A) equipped with 2 separation branches and 2 sampling loops. The first separation branch includes 2 semicapillary columns (HP Plot Q and Molesieve 5 A), a Thermal Conductivity Detector (TCD), a Flame Ionization Detector (FID) and a methanizer, while the second separation branch contains a capillary column (CP-Sil 5B) and a second FID. In a typical experiment, the reactor was outgassed under vacuum at 80 °C and then purged with Ar (100 mL min^{-1} during 1 h). Then, the reactor was filled with the CO₂:H₂O mixture and kept 1 h in the dark to establish an adsorption–desorption balance. Then, UV illumination was turned on to start the photocatalytic experiments (15 h total elapsed time). Blank experiments were conducted to verify the absence of any C-production under dark conditions or without any catalyst under UV illumination

Photonic efficiency (α) calculation. Photonic efficiencies were calculated as the ratio between the reaction rate and the incident photon flux, according to Eq. (2):

$$\bar{z} = \frac{dN/dt}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} q_{p,\lambda}^0 dt} \quad (2)$$

where dN/dt represents the CH_4 production rate and $q_{p,\lambda}^0$ is the incident spectral photon flux (250 – 400 nm). The incident spectral photon flux was calculated from the lamps emission spectra (see **Fig. S1B**), recorded with a StellarNet UVNb-50 radiometer connected to an optical fibre. The superscript 0 (zero) emphasizes that the incident number of photons (prior to absorption) is also considered.

Electron consumption rate (R_{electron}) calculation. R_{electron} of P25 and anatase in the CO_2 photoreduction process was calculated according Eq. (3):

$$R_{\text{electron}} = 2 \cdot r(\text{CO}) + 6 \cdot r(\text{CH}_3\text{OH}) + 8 \cdot r(\text{CH}_4) + 12 \cdot r(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4) + 14 \cdot r(\text{C}_2\text{H}_6) \quad (3)$$

where R_{electron} is the rate of electron consumption; Numbers represent the number of electrons involved in the formation of each product; $r(x)$ are the corresponding product rates ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$).

3. Results and discussion

The crystallinity of TiO_2 anatase and P25 samples was studied by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements. **Fig. S2** shows the typical diffraction profiles of anatase (ICDD pattern No. 21-1272. space group: $I4_1/amd$), and the coexistence of anatase and rutile phases (ICDD pattern No. 21-1276. Space group: $P4_2/mnm$) in P25 sample. In this case, the relative abundance of both crystalline phases in P25 is estimated to be ca. 89/11% (anatase/rutile), before and after calcination, according to the intensity of anatase (1 0 1) and rutile (1 1 0) reflections. This ratio is higher than the theoretical 70:30 generally reported in literature, although it is consistent with previous publications and the lack of consensus of the exact crystalline composition of this material [43,44]. The overestimation of anatase phase could be due to the presence of an amorphous phase that is not observed

by XRD [45]. The anatase:rutile ratio obtained in this work is associated with the calcination conditions, which favour the predominant content of anatase without promoting any other phase transition. The crystal size of anatase nanoparticles was found to be 14.5 nm, according to Scherrer equation; while crystal sizes in P25 were 21.1 nm and 33.8 nm for anatase and rutile phases, respectively. N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms (**Fig. S3**) show similar shapes (Type II) for both samples with type H3 hysteresis loops [46]. The BET surface area of anatase and P25 are 166 m² g⁻¹ and 47 m² g⁻¹, respectively. The morphology and particle size distribution of both samples were analyzed by TEM and are depicted in **Fig. 1**. Anatase sample shows nanoparticles with irregular morphology and an average diameter of ca. 11 nm (**Fig. 1A-B**). P25 nanoparticles also show irregular morphologies (**Fig. 1C-D**) and a wider size distribution (mean particle size of 20-25 nm). These results correlate well with the superior crystal size of anatase and rutile in P25 calculated from XRD.

Fig. S4 shows the diffuse reflectance UV-vis spectra of both samples. Both spectra show an intense absorption band in the UV region ($\lambda < 400$ nm) with two contributions centred at ca. 220 and 300 nm, which are associated with the formation of octahedral Ti³⁺ species upon UV light excitation (via electron transfer O²⁻ → Ti⁴⁺) [31,47]. The band gap energy (E_g) was calculated by Tauc plot and is 3.09 eV and 3.06 eV for anatase and P25, respectively (**Fig. S4B-C**). Despite the absorption profiles of anatase TiO₂ and P25 are very similar, the anatase-rutile composite in P25 brings about significant modulation of electronic parameters such as ionization potential, electron affinity and the work function, which are relevant properties for photocatalytic applications. We estimated the work function of the photocatalysts from XPS measurements, by measuring the

secondary photoelectrons cut-off binding energy of samples under a 5 V bias. The bias is used to separate secondary photoelectrons of the samples from those from of spectrometer. **Fig. 2A** shows the spectra of the samples in the cut-off region after Fermi level correction. The Fermi level was estimated from a Ag sample under the same bias of the photocatalysts samples. Binding energies of photo electrons at the cut-off edge in the spectra of anatase TiO₂ and P25 were respectively determined at 1482.29 eV and 1482.52 eV. **Fig. S5** shows that the cut-off energy position in different spots of the samples is highly reproducible. Considering the excitation energy, Al K α 1 (1486.703 eV), the work function values of our anatase TiO₂ and P25 samples are 4.4 eV and 4.2 eV, respectively. With the energy position of the valence band onset (**Fig. 2B** and **2C**) the ionization potential can be estimated as 7.6 eV and 7.4 eV for anatase TiO₂ and P25, respectively. The modulation of such electronic properties is a direct consequence of the type II staggered band gap alignment between anatase TiO₂ and rutile TiO₂ [39], in which the conduction band minimum of the rutile phase possesses higher energy levels. A lower work function in P25 may favour the transfer of photogenerated charge carriers at the interface for more effective photocatalytic reactions, which is in good agreement with the low interface charge transfer resistance observed in the EIS studies, as it will be shown below.

3.1. Gas-phase CO₂ photoreduction

CO₂ photoreduction with water vapor over TiO₂ anatase mainly promoted the formation of CO and H₂ under UV illumination (**Fig. 3A-B** and **Table S1**), reaching maximum production rates of 25.5 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ and 7.6 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$, respectively. Additional minority products such as CH₄, CH₃OH and C₂H₆ were also found at lower amounts (**Table S1**). On the other hand, TiO₂ P25 showed a similar product

distribution as anatase, but a higher photoactivity in terms of overall cumulative productions and selectivity. Specifically, CO production increased by 11% and CH₄ evolution more than doubled (ca. 2.6-fold increase) that of anatase (**Table S1**). Accordingly, P25 showed a lower selectivity to CO in favor of CH₄, C₂ products and H₂ evolution (**Fig. 3C**).

Further, the weighted productivities of both samples was compared in terms of their electron consumption rate [14], which evaluates the C-production considering the number of electrons involved in the formation of each product. P25 showed a 2.1-fold higher electron consumption rate than anatase (**Fig. 3D** and **Table S1**), which is related to a higher CO₂ photoreduction efficiency. Moreover, P25 also showed a 2.6-times higher photonic efficiency towards CH₄ than that of anatase (**Table S1**), corroborating the beneficial effect of the mixture anatase-rutile for CO₂ photoreduction.

3.2. Photocarrier characterization

A photoelectrochemical study was performed to shed light into the photocatalytic performance of the two materials under study (P25 and anatase) from their fundamental semiconducting point of view. The photoelectrochemical characterization was performed in 0.5 M Na₂SO₃ under three-electrode configuration, including electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. **Fig. 4A** shows the j-V response of P25 and anatase under chopped illumination, measured by linear sweep voltammetry. Both samples show a positive photocurrent, confirming the expected behaviour of TiO₂ as a n-type semiconductor and as a photoanode. A high surface recombination was observed in both samples at V < 0.5 V vs RHE, as reflected from the spikes present at these applied biases in the j-V curves. However, from 0.5 V vs RHE onwards, the spikes disappeared while the

photocurrent grew, as a consequence of an enhanced charge transfer with the concomitant reduction in the recombination. The P25 photoanode showed an improved onset and a ~ 4.5 times higher photocurrent density than the anatase one, in good agreement with the observed photocatalytic activity. Apart from an intrinsic higher photoactivity in P25 as result of the combination of rutile and anatase phases, P25 sample also showed a higher homogeneity in the fabricated thin-films (see **Fig. S6-S8**) leading to continuous domains, which has been reported to increase the lifetime of the photogenerated carriers [48]. Further mechanistic insights were extracted from electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements under dark and illumination conditions [49]. The experimental impedance data were fitted with a Randles' circuit (since a single arc was observed in the Nyquist plots). This equivalent circuit accounts from the contact and wiring, reflected in the series resistance (R_s), and the interface between the sample and the electrolyte reflected in the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and the capacitance (C), as schematized in the inset in **Fig. 4D**. The R_s (**Fig. 4B**) shows a flat behaviour with the applied potential for both samples and do not shown any change under illumination conditions, as expected, being in the 39 – 42 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ range. The R_{ct} (**Fig. 4C**) shows a decrease under illumination, as expected in a photoelectrode. On the other hand, R_{ct} shows lower values for P25 than for anatase, in good agreement with the higher photocurrent observed in P25, as a consequence of the adequate type II alignment between the two phases, as shown by XPS. Additionally, in both samples, the extracted capacitances (**Fig. 4D**) show a decrease with the applied potential, specially under large anodic bias, as a consequence of an enhanced charge extraction to the electrolyte, as previously reported in TiO_2 photoanodes [50,51]. In addition,

P25 sample shows a lower capacitance than anatase, due to a lower accumulation of photogenerated holes at the TiO₂/electrolyte interface, also explaining the enhanced performance of this sample [52].

Further, to deeply understand the electron transfer mechanism in both TiO₂ samples, we developed spectroscopic studies from the ns to ms timescale by photoluminescence (PL), time-resolved PL (TRPL) and transient absorption spectroscopy (TAS). **Fig. 5A** shows similar PL profiles for P25 and anatase. Both samples show a broad emission band in the region between 350 and 700 nm (3.5 - 2.1 eV) (**Fig. S9**), in which the first peak at 396 nm is assigned to the band to band radiative recombination after UV excitation [53]. Besides, the signals located in from 400 to 700 nm are associated with different charge recombination processes in intermediate band gap states of the material [54,55]. In particular, the band centered at 423 nm (**Fig. S9**) is assigned to recombination processes of self-trapped excitons in anatase or free excitons in rutile [53]. It should be noted that the intensities found in the emission bands of P25 were lower than those of anatase, suggesting a longer lifetime of photogenerated charges and a slower recombination rate. This finding agrees well with the higher degree of crystallinity of P25 than anatase, which is associated with a lower presence of surface defects that can act as recombination centers [31,39], thus contributing to lower PL intensities.

The corresponding photoluminescence lifetimes (τ_F) were fitted by a triexponential function obtaining an average lifetime of $\tau_F = 2.50$ and 3.54 ns for anatase and P25, respectively (**Fig. 5A**, inset). The slight increase in P25 lifetime is associated with the charge transfer between rutile and anatase phases. In this regard, Li et al. [33] recently reported the migration of photogenerated electrons

from rutile to anatase in a TiO₂ heterophase junction, and the migration of photogenerated holes in the opposite direction.

Next, we performed transient absorption spectroscopy (TAS) to confirm the different charge-separation mechanism in both TiO₂ samples. **Fig. 5B** (left) shows the transient absorption (TA) spectrum of anatase after 20 ns laser pulse ($\lambda_{\text{exc}}=355$ nm, 1.5 mJ, N₂) excitation, which reveals a continuous absorption in all spectrum window due to the electron-hole separation [56]. In contrast, the TA spectrum of P25 showed an increase in ΔOD due to the charge transfer between anatase and rutile phases in the heterojunction (**Fig. 5B** right).

Next, the temporal profile of P25 ($\lambda_{\text{observation}} = 460$ nm, corresponding to the maximum transient absorption reported for TiO₂ anatase [57–60]) showed an almost 2-fold higher lifetime ($\tau = \sim 95$ ns) than that of anatase ($\tau = \sim 56$ ns) during the first 600 ns after pulse excitation (**Fig. 5C**). Furthermore, a delay in the top of the signal was observed for P25 (**Fig. 5C**), as an indication of an interfacial charge transfer from rutile to anatase phase. We have previously observed this phenomenon in inorganic-organic heterojunctions, based on TiO₂ anatase and Conjugated Porous Polymers (CPP) [14,61].

Then, the temporal profile in the μs timescale was compared with those obtained in the ns range (**Fig. S10**). Again, P25 showed a longer lifetime than anatase in all the kinetic range (recorded up to 6 μs), confirming a slow-down of the electron-hole recombination process. Our findings show that the two-phase heterojunction in P25 sample promotes the migration of photogenerated electrons from rutile to anatase phase (**Fig. 5D**), thus reducing the probability charge recombination [40,62–64]. The mechanism of electron-hole (e⁻/h⁺) pair in the heterojunction

(anatase-rutile) on the P25 surface is shown in **Fig 5D**. Under UV light, the presence of Ti^{3+} and oxygen vacancies by direct UV absorption can effectively narrow down the bandgap of both rutile and anatase phases. The electrons are transferred from the conduction band (CB) of rutile to the CB of the anatase. At the same time, the generated holes from the valence band (VB) of anatase are transferred to the VB of rutile in the P25 photocatalyst. The longer lifetime of charge carriers explains the greater photocatalytic activity of P25 (**Fig. 3**), and especially its higher driving force towards more electron-demanding products (i.e. CH_4 and C_2).

4. Conclusions

The beneficial interaction between anatase and rutile in the two-phase heterojunction P25 is demonstrated in gas-phase CO_2 photoreduction. P25 shows a higher overall C_1 - C_2 production than sole anatase TiO_2 and, particularly, a higher driving force towards more electron-demanding products such as CH_4 and C_2 . This superior CO_2 photoreduction efficiency is associated with the interfacial migration of photogenerated electrons from rutile to anatase phase, which results in slower electron-hole recombination rates. The electron transfer from rutile to anatase is demonstrated by TAS measurements, and supported by EIS and XPS. These studies revealed a lower interface charge transfer resistance and a lower work function in P25, which support the transfer of photogenerated charge carriers at the interface for more effective photocatalytic performance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Laura Collado: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing, Funding acquisition.

Miguel García-Tecedor: Methodology, Writing, Funding acquisition. **Miguel**

Gomez-Mendoza: Methodology, Writing. **Alejandro Herrero:** Writing. **Freddy E. Oropeza:** Methodology, Writing – review editing. **Marta Liras:** Writing – review editing, Funding acquisition. **Víctor A. de la Peña O’Shea:** Conceptualization, Writing – review editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

L.C. acknowledges funding from the project ARMONIA (PID2020–119125RJ-I00) funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033. Additional funding was received from TED2021-129999A-C33, NovaCO2 (PID2020-118593RB-C22) and the grant PLEC2021–007906 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/50110001103. Financial support was also received from the “European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR”; AEI-MINECO/FEDER (NHympha Project, PID2019–106315RB-I00); “Comunidad de Madrid” regional government; and the European Structural Funds (FotoArt-CM project, S2018/NMT-4367).

FIGURES

Fig. 1. TEM images and particle size distribution for anatase (A, B and E) and P25 (C, D and F).

Fig. 2. (A) Photoelectron spectra in the cutoff region for anatase TiO₂ and P25 with external bias of 5V; photoelectron emission spectra in the valence band region of anatase (B) and (C) P25, showing the onset energy position.

Fig. 3. Cumulative productions (μmol g⁻¹) for anatase (A) and P25 (B) in CO₂ photoreduction under 15 h of UV illumination (error bars ±5%); (C) Product selectivity (%): H₂ (blue), CO (orange), CH₄ (green), C₂ (purple); (D) CH₄ evolution (green bars) and cumulative Weighted carbon production (blue bars).

Fig. 4. Photoelectrochemical response of the samples under study in 0.5 M Na₂SO₃ under three-electrode configuration. (A) Linear sweep voltammetry under chopped illumination acquired on the P25 (blue) and Anatase (red) samples. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy analysis showing (B) the Series Resistance, (C) the Charge Transfer Resistance and (D) the Capacitance. Empty symbols correspond to measurements under light, while filled symbols correspond to measurements under dark.

Fig. 5. (A) Photoluminescence (PL, $\lambda_{exc} = 300$ nm) for anatase (red) and P25 (blue). Inset: Corresponding Time-resolved PL ($\lambda_{exc} = 372$ nm). (B) Transient absorption spectra ($\lambda_{exc} = 355$ nm) for anatase (red) and P25 (blue) in aqueous dispersed solutions at different timescales. (C) Transient decay traces monitored at 460 nm ($\lambda_{exc} = 355$ nm) for anatase (red) and P25 (blue) recorded up to 200 ns after laser pulse. (D) Schematics of the main interfacial charge transfer pathway in the heterojunction anatase:rutile: light absorption (solid black line), recombination (dash black lines), electron transfer (red line) and hole transfer (blue line).

References

- [1] United Nations, Paris Agreement, (2015).
- [2] IPCC, AR5 Synthesis Report: Climate Change 2014, 2014.
- [3] United Nations, Glasgow Climate Pact, (2021).
- [4] G. Nicoletti, N. Arcuri, G. Nicoletti, R. Bruno, A technical and environmental comparison between hydrogen and some fossil fuels, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 89 (2015) 205–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2014.09.057>.
- [5] S. Chu, A. Majumdar, Opportunities and challenges for a sustainable energy future, *Nature*. 488 (2012) 294–303.
- [6] R.C. Armstrong, C. Wolfram, K.P. De Jong, R. Gross, N.S. Lewis, B. Boardman, A.J. Ragauskas, K. Ehrhardt-Martinez, G. Crabtree, M. V. Ramana, The frontiers of energy, *Nat. Energy*. 1 (2016) 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nenergy.2015.20>.
- [7] L. Collado, M. Gomez-Mendoza, M. García-Tecedor, F.E. Oropeza, A. Reynal, J.R. Durrant, D.P. Serrano, V.A. De La Peña O’Shea, Towards the improvement of methane production in CO₂ photoreduction using Bi₂WO₆/TiO₂ heterostructures, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 324 (2023) 122206–122215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2022.122206>.
- [8] L. Collado, P. Jana, B. Sierra, J.M. Coronado, P. Pizarro, D.P. Serrano, V.A. de la Peña O’Shea, Enhancement of hydrocarbon production via artificial photosynthesis due to synergetic effect of Ag supported on TiO₂ and ZnO semiconductors, *Chem. Eng. J.* 224 (2013) 128–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2012.12.053>.
- [9] L. Collado, P. Reñones, J. Feroso, F. Fresno, L. Garrido, V. Pérez-Dieste, C. Escudero, M.D. Hernández-Alonso, J.M. Coronado, D.P. Serrano, V.A. de la Peña O’Shea, The role of the surface acidic/basic centers and redox sites on TiO₂ in the photocatalytic CO₂ reduction, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 303 (2022) 120931–120942. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2021.120931>.
- [10] V.A. de la Peña O’Shea, D.P. Serrano, J.M. Coronado, Current Challenges of CO₂ Photocatalytic Reduction Over Semiconductors Using Sunlight BT - From Molecules to Materials: Pathways to Artificial Photosynthesis, in: E.A. Rozhkova, K. Ariga (Eds.), Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2015: pp. 171–191. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-13800-8_7.
- [11] M. Liras, M. Barawi, V.A. De La Peña O’Shea, Hybrid materials based on conjugated polymers and inorganic semiconductors as photocatalysts: From environmental to energy applications, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 48 (2019) 5454–5487. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9cs00377k>.
- [12] J.K. Stolarczyk, S. Bhattacharyya, L. Polavarapu, J. Feldmann, Challenges and Prospects in Solar Water Splitting and CO₂ Reduction with Inorganic and Hybrid Nanostructures, *ACS Catal.* 8 (2018) 3602–3635. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.8b00791>.
- [13] F. Fresno, I.J. Villar-García, L. Collado, E. Alfonso-González, P. Reñones, M. Barawi, V.A. de la Peña O’Shea, Mechanistic View of the Main Current Issues in Photocatalytic CO₂ Reduction, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 9 (2018) 7192–7204. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.8b02336>.

- [14] L. Collado, T. Naranjo, M. Gomez-Mendoza, C.G. López-Calixto, F.E. Oropeza, M. Liras, J. Marugán, V.A. de la Peña O'Shea, Conjugated Porous Polymers Based on BODIPY and BOPHY Dyes in Hybrid Heterojunctions for Artificial Photosynthesis, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* (2021) 2105384–2105396. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202105384>.
- [15] M. Barawi, L. Collado, M. Gomez-Mendoza, F.E. Oropeza, M. Liras, V.A. de la Peña O'Shea, Conjugated Porous Polymers: Ground-Breaking Materials for Solar Energy Conversion, *Adv. Energy Mater.* (2021) 2101530–2101561. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202101530>.
- [16] L. Collado, A. Reynal, J.M. Coronado, D.P. Serrano, J.R. Durrant, V.A. de la Peña O'Shea, Effect of Au surface plasmon nanoparticles on the selective CO₂ photoreduction to CH₄, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 178 (2015) 177–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2014.09.032>.
- [17] A. Pougin, M. Dilla, J. Strunk, Identification and exclusion of intermediates of photocatalytic CO₂ reduction on TiO₂ under conditions of highest purity, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 18 (2016) 10809–10817. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5cp07148h>.
- [18] C.-C. Yang, Y.-H. Yu, B. van der Linden, J.C.S. Wu, G. Mul, Artificial photosynthesis over crystalline TiO₂-based catalysts: fact or fiction?, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 132 (2010) 8398–406. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja101318k>.
- [19] Art Leaf Database - CO₂ valorization by Artificial Photosynthesis. Available at: <http://www.artleafs.eu>, (n.d.).
- [20] C.O. Robichaud, A.E. Uyar, M.R. Darby, L.G. Zucker, M.R. Wiesner, Estimates of Upper Bounds and Trends in Nano-TiO₂ Production As a Basis for Exposure Assessment, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 43 (2009) 4227–4233. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es8032549>.
- [21] Y. Lan, Y. Lu, Z. Ren, Mini review on photocatalysis of titanium dioxide nanoparticles and their solar applications, *Nano Energy.* 2 (2013) 1031–1045. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2013.04.002>.
- [22] S. Protti, A. Albin, N. Serpone, Photocatalytic generation of solar fuels from the reduction of H₂O and CO₂: a look at the patent literature, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 16 (2014) 19790–19827. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4CP02828G>.
- [23] Z. Rui, S. Wu, C. Peng, H. Ji, Comparison of TiO₂ Degussa P25 with anatase and rutile crystalline phases for methane combustion, *Chem. Eng. J.* 243 (2014) 254–264. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2014.01.010>.
- [24] J. Ryu, W. Choi, Substrate-Specific Photocatalytic Activities of TiO₂ and Multiactivity Test for Water Treatment Application, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 42 (2008) 294–300. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es071470x>.
- [25] T. Ohno, K. Sarukawa, K. Tokieda, M. Matsumura, Morphology of a TiO₂ photocatalyst (Degussa, P25) consisting on Anatase and Rutile crystalline phases, *J. Catal.* 203 (2011) 82–86.
- [26] X. Jiang, M. Manawan, T. Feng, R. Qian, T. Zhao, G. Zhou, F. Kong, Q. Wang, S. Dai, J.H. Pan, Anatase and rutile in evonik aeroxide P25: Heterojunctioned or individual nanoparticles?, *Catal. Today.* 300 (2018) 12–17. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2017.06.010>.

- [27] T. Ohno, K. Sarukawa, K. Tokieda, M. Matsumura, Morphology of a TiO₂ Photocatalyst (Degussa, P-25) Consisting of Anatase and Rutile Crystalline Phases, *J. Catal.* 203 (2001) 82–86. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jcat.2001.3316>.
- [28] O. Núñez, D. Sattayamuk, T. Saelee, H. Yamashita, Y. Kuwahara, K. Mori, P. Prasertdam, S. Prasertdam, A closer look inside TiO₂ (P25) photocatalytic CO₂/HCO₃⁻ reduction with water. Methane rate and selectivity enhancements, *Chem. Eng. J.* 409 (2021) 128141. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.128141>.
- [29] P. Reñones, A. Moya, F. Fresno, L. Collado, J.J. Vilatela, V.A. De La Peña O’Shea, Hierarchical TiO₂ nanofibres as photocatalyst for CO₂ reduction: Influence of morphology and phase composition on catalytic activity, *J. CO₂ Util.* 15 (2016) 24–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2016.04.002>.
- [30] N. Shehzad, M. Tahir, K. Johari, T. Murugesan, M. Hussain, A critical review on TiO₂ based photocatalytic CO₂ reduction system: Strategies to improve efficiency, *J. CO₂ Util.* 26 (2018) 98–122. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2018.04.026>.
- [31] M. Kapilashrami, Y. Zhang, Y.-S. Liu, A. Hagfeldt, J. Guo, Probing the Optical Property and Electronic Structure of TiO₂ Nanomaterials for Renewable Energy Applications., *Chem. Rev.* 114 (2014) 9662–9707. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr5000893>.
- [32] F. Paquin, J. Rivnay, A. Salleo, N. Stingelin, C. Silva, Cubic anatase TiO₂ nanocrystals with enhanced photocatalytic CO₂ reduction activity, *Chem. Commun.* 51 (2015) 7950–7953. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b000000x>.
- [33] J. Qu, J. He, H. Li, Q. Jiang, M. Li, Q. Kong, M. Shi, R. Li, C. Li, Unraveling the Role of Interface in Photogenerated Charge Separation at the Anatase/Rutile Heterophase Junction, *J. Phys. Chem. C.* 127 (2023) 768–775. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.2c07482>.
- [34] V. Pfeifer, P. Erhart, S. Li, K. Rachut, J. Morasch, J. Brötz, P. Reckers, T. Mayer, S. Rühle, A. Zaban, I. Mora Seró, J. Bisquert, W. Jaegermann, A. Klein, Energy Band Alignment between Anatase and Rutile TiO₂, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 4 (2013) 4182–4187. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jz402165b>.
- [35] G. Xiong, R. Shao, T.C. Droubay, A.G. Joly, K.M. Beck, S.A. Chambers, W.P. Hess, Photoemission Electron Microscopy of TiO₂ Anatase Films Embedded with Rutile Nanocrystals, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 17 (2007) 2133–2138. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.200700146>.
- [36] P. Deák, B. Aradi, T. Frauenheim, Band Lineup and Charge Carrier Separation in Mixed Rutile-Anatase Systems, *J. Phys. Chem. C.* 115 (2011) 3443–3446.
- [37] D.C. Hurum, K.A. Gray, T. Rajh, M.C. Thurnauer, Recombination Pathways in the Degussa P25 Formulation of TiO₂: Surface versus Lattice Mechanisms, *J. Phys. Chem. B.* 109 (2005) 977–980. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp045395d>.
- [38] A. Kafizas, X. Wang, S.R. Pendlebury, P. Barnes, M. Ling, C. Sotelo-Vazquez, R. Quesada-Cabrera, C. Li, I.P. Parkin, J.R. Durrant, Where Do Photogenerated Holes Go in Anatase:Rutile TiO₂? A Transient Absorption Spectroscopy Study of Charge Transfer and Lifetime, *J. Phys. Chem. A.* 120 (2016) 715–723. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.5b11567>.

- [39] D.O. Scanlon, C.W. Dunnill, J. Buckeridge, S.A. Shevlin, A.J. Logsdail, S.M. Woodley, C.R.A. Catlow, M.J. Powell, R.G. Palgrave, I.P. Parkin, G.W. Watson, T.W. Keal, P. Sherwood, A. Walsh, A.A. Sokol, Band alignment of rutile and anatase TiO₂, *Nat. Mater.* 12 (2013) 798–801. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat3697>.
- [40] D.C. Hurum, A.G. Agrios, K.A. Gray, T. Rajh, M.C. Thurnauer, Explaining the Enhanced Photocatalytic Activity of Degussa P25 Mixed-Phase TiO₂ Using EPR, *J. Phys. Chem. B.* 107 (2003) 4545–4549. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp0273934>.
- [41] R.A. Spurr, H. Myers, Quantitative Analysis of Anatase-Rutile Mixtures with an X-Ray Diffractometer, *Anal. Chem.* 29 (1957) 760–762.
- [42] M. García-Tecedor, G. Gorni, F. Oropeza, L. Gómez, M. Liras, V.A. de la Peña O’Shea, M. Barawi, Unravelling nanostructured Nb-doped TiO₂ dual band behaviour in smart windows by in situ spectroscopies, *J. Mater. Chem. A.* 10 (2022) 19994–20004. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ta03239b>.
- [43] S. Phomma, T. Wutikhun, P. Kasamechong, T. Eksangsri, C. Sapcharoenkun, Effect of calcination temperature on photocatalytic activity of synthesized TiO₂ nanoparticles via wet ball milling sol-gel method, *Appl. Sci.* 10 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10030993>.
- [44] B. Ohtani, O.O. Prieto-Mahaney, D. Li, R. Abe, What is Degussa (Evonik) P25? Crystalline composition analysis, reconstruction from isolated pure particles and photocatalytic activity test, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A Chem.* 216 (2010) 179–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphotochem.2010.07.024>.
- [45] B. Ohtani, Preparing Articles on Photocatalysis—Beyond the Illusions, Misconceptions, and Speculation, *Chem. Lett.* 37 (2008) 216–229.
- [46] K.S.W. Sing, D.H. Everett, R.A.W. Haul, L. Moscou, R.A. Pierotti, J. Rouquerol, T. Siemieniowska, Reporting Physisorption Data for Gas/Solid Systems with Special Reference to the Determination of Surface Area and Porosity, *Pure Appl. Chem.* 57 (1985) 603–619.
- [47] H. Nur, H. Hamdan, Hydrophobic fluorinated TiO₂–ZrO₂ as catalyst in epoxidation of 1-octene with aqueous hydrogen peroxide, *Mater. Lett.* 60 (2006) 2274–2277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2005.12.139>.
- [48] N. Aiga, Q. Jia, K. Watanabe, A. Kudo, T. Sugimoto, Y. Matsumoto, Electron-phonon coupling dynamics at oxygen evolution sites of visible-light-driven photocatalyst: Bismuth vanadate, *J. Phys. Chem. C.* 117 (2013) 9881–9886. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp4013027>.
- [49] D. Cardenas-Morcoso, A. Bou, S. Ravishankar, M. García-Tecedor, S. Gimenez, J. Bisquert, Intensity-Modulated Photocurrent Spectroscopy for Solar Energy Conversion Devices: What Does a Negative Value Mean?, *ACS Energy Lett.* 5 (2020) 187–191. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.9b02555>.
- [50] M.N. Shaddad, D. Cardenas-Morcoso, M. García-Tecedor, F. Fabregat-Santiago, J. Bisquert, A.M. Al-Mayouf, S. Gimenez, TiO₂ Nanotubes for Solar Water Splitting: Vacuum Annealing and Zr Doping Enhance Water Oxidation Kinetics, *ACS Omega.* 4 (2019) 16095–16102. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.9b02297>.
- [51] J. Barrio, C. Gibaja, M. García-Tecedor, L. Abisdri, I. Torres, N. Karjule, S. Giménez, M. Shalom, F. Zamora, Electrophoretic deposition of

- antimonene for photoelectrochemical applications, *Appl. Mater. Today*. 20 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2020.100714>.
- [52] M. Barawi, M. Gomez-Mendoza, F.E. Oropeza, G. Gorni, I.J. Villar-Garcia, S. Giménez, V.A. de la Peña O'Shea, M. García-Tecedor, Laser-Reduced BiVO₄ for Enhanced Photoelectrochemical Water Splitting, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*. (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscami.2c07451>.
- [53] L. Kernazhitsky, V. Shymanovska, T. Gavrilko, V. Naumov, L. Fedorenko, V. Kshnyakin, J. Baran, Room temperature photoluminescence of anatase and rutile TiO₂ powders, *J. Lumin.* 146 (2014) 199–204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlumin.2013.09.068>.
- [54] J. Liqiang, Q. Yichun, W. Baiqi, L. Shudan, J. Baojiang, Y. Libin, F. Wei, F. Honggang, S. Jiazhong, Review of photoluminescence performance of nano-sized semiconductor materials and its relationships with photocatalytic activity, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*. 90 (2006) 1773–1787. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2005.11.007>.
- [55] B. Liu, L. Wen, X. Zhao, The photoluminescence spectroscopic study of anatase TiO₂ prepared by magnetron sputtering, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 106 (2007) 350–353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2007.06.012>.
- [56] A.O.T. Patrocínio, J. Schneider, M.D. França, L.M. Santos, B.P. Caixeta, A.E.H. Machado, D.W. Bahnemann, Charge carrier dynamics and photocatalytic behavior of TiO₂ nanopowders submitted to hydrothermal or conventional heat treatment, *RSC Adv.* 5 (2015) 70536–70545. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5ra13291f>.
- [57] J. Tang, J.R. Durrant, D.R. Klug, Mechanism of photocatalytic water splitting in TiO₂. Reaction of water with photoholes, importance of charge carrier dynamics, and evidence for four-hole chemistry., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 130 (2008) 13885–13891. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja8034637>.
- [58] R. Katoh, M. Murai, A. Furube, Transient absorption spectra of nanocrystalline TiO₂ films at high excitation density, *Chem. Phys. Lett.* 500 (2010) 309–312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cplett.2010.10.045>.
- [59] R. Qian, H. Zong, J. Schneider, G. Zhou, T. Zhao, Y. Li, J. Yang, D.W. Bahnemann, J.H. Pan, Charge carrier trapping, recombination and transfer during TiO₂ photocatalysis: An overview, *Catal. Today*. 335 (2019) 78–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2018.10.053>.
- [60] J. Schneider, M. Matsuoka, M. Takeuchi, J. Zhang, Y. Horiuchi, M. Anpo, D.W. Bahnemann, Understanding TiO₂ Photocatalysis: Mechanisms and Materials., *Chem. Rev.* 114 (2014) 9919–9986. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr5001892>.
- [61] C.G. López-Calixto, M. Barawi, M. Gomez-Mendoza, F.E. Oropeza, F. Fresno, M. Liras, V.A. de la Peña O'Shea, Hybrids Based on BOPHY-Conjugated Porous Polymers as Photocatalysts for Hydrogen Production: Insight into the Charge Transfer Pathway, *ACS Catal.* 10 (2020) 9804–9812. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.0c01346>.
- [62] Y. Mi, Y. Weng, Band Alignment and Controllable Electron Migration between Rutile and Anatase TiO₂, *Sci. Rep.* 5 (2015) 11482. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep11482>.
- [63] Y.-C. Yen, J.-A. Chen, S. Ou, Y.-S. Chen, K.-J. Lin, Plasmon-Enhanced Photocurrent using Gold Nanoparticles on a Three-Dimensional TiO₂

- Nanowire-Web Electrode, *Sci. Rep.* 7 (2017) 42524. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep42524>.
- [64] L.S. Daniel, H. Nagai, M. Sato, Absorption spectra and photocurrent densities of Ag nanoparticle/TiO₂ composite thin films with various amounts of Ag, *J. Mater. Sci.* 48 (2013) 7162–7170. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-013-7533-0>.